

The Influence of Translation Method on Language Skills

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ABSTRACT

Context: It should be noted that one of the most important functions of using the native language in foreign language lessons is translation from the native language into a foreign language and vice versa. **Goal:** This study is aimed at studying the positive and negative aspects of using the translation method in foreign language lessons. **Design:** The study also used an online survey and statistical research. Moreover, it discusses the role and history of translation in teaching a foreign language, the object of research is the process of teaching foreign languages. The subject of the study is the place, functions, advantages and disadvantages of translation and its systemic representation in mastering a foreign language. **Environment and participants:** To achieve this goal, the following main tasks are solved in the study:

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1. Conducting a survey on "Technical universities and philological universities in the use of translation exercises" among teachers of foreign languages
2. Conducting a study among students of a technical specialized university based on the results of a survey

Keywords: translation, foreign language, native language, technical universities, philological universities

A influência do método de tradução nas habilidades linguísticas

RESUMO

Contexto: Cabe destacar que uma das funções mais importantes do uso da língua nativa nas aulas de língua estrangeira é a tradução da língua nativa para a língua estrangeira e vice-versa. **Objetivo:** Este estudo tem como objetivo estudar os aspectos positivos e negativos do uso do método de tradução nas aulas de língua estrangeira. **Design:** O estudo também utilizou uma pesquisa online e pesquisa estatística. Além disso, discute o papel e a história da tradução no ensino de línguas estrangeiras, o objeto de pesquisa é o processo de ensino de línguas estrangeiras. O tema do estudo é o lugar, funções, vantagens e desvantagens da tradução e sua representação sistêmica no domínio de uma língua estrangeira. **Ambiente e participantes:** Para atingir este objetivo, as seguintes tarefas principais são resolvidas no estudo:

1. Realização de uma pesquisa sobre "Universidades técnicas e universidades filológicas no uso de exercícios de tradução" entre professores de línguas estrangeiras
2. Realização de um estudo entre estudantes de uma universidade técnica especializada com base nos resultados de uma pesquisa

Palavras-chave: tradução, língua estrangeira, língua nativa, universidades técnicas, universidades filológicas

INTRODUCTION

Translation has always performed the most important social function, making it possible for people to communicate interlingually. Perhaps nothing in the history and modern methodology of teaching foreign language has caused so

much controversy, so many conflicting assessments and opposing opinions, as the question of the need and possibility of using translation in teaching to foreigners. Estimates range from the most positive to categorically negative.

Until the beginning of the 1960s, the teaching of a foreign language was dominated by the grammar-translation method, in which translation was the basis of education. “The goal of teaching in these years was considered to be the understanding of the readable text and the ability to translate it, and not the development of independent speech skills” (Pulkina, 1962, p.51)

In the 60s, 70s and 10s, methodologists developed a negative attitude towards translation as a means of teaching, it is proved that mastering a foreign language can occur without the development of translation skills, and hence the conclusion is made about the uselessness and even undesirability of using translation when teaching speech in a foreign language. First of all, the difference between the functional systems of translation and monolingual speech activity in the language learned in childhood is noted. A.N. Leontiev wrote:

“It is known that bilingual children, i.e. people who speak two languages roughly equally can never translate from one of these languages into the other. This fact directly indicates that we have two different functional systems here and that, despite the ability to speak and understand speech in two languages, such children will not develop a functional translation system at all.” (Leontiev, 1977)

Further, the researcher asks a rhetorical question:

“Of course, it is possible to form speech in a foreign language through the formation of a functional translation system - just like you can go, for example, from Moscow to Bucharest via Paris, but why, you ask, is this necessary?” (Leontiev, 1977)

Following this logic, a number of methodologists actually came to a complete denial of the possibility of using translation as a methodological tool in teaching foreign languages and even expressed annoyance at the fact that “the passion for translation, unfortunately, has not cooled down yet” (Passov, 1977).

METHODS

The use of translational exercises in teaching foreign languages has a long and difficult history and is a debatable and controversial issue. In recent decades,

there have been various theories that exclude translational exercises from the learning process. Nevertheless, the attitude towards it still remains ambiguous, and the number of his opponents is not inferior to the number of supporters. One of the main reasons for the negative attitude towards translation is that it is strongly associated with the Grammar-translation method of teaching a foreign language in which the translation of sentences from the native language into a foreign language was used to understand the meaning of the text and train the use of language funds. This method was characterized by:

- a) presentation of proposals outside the communicative context;
- b) "artificiality" of tasks, lack of a communicative orientation;
- c) the priority of studying grammar rules and vocabulary;
- d) lack of tasks for listening and speaking;
- e) the formation of a false idea among students about the existence of stable and fixed bilingual correspondences, with the help of which it is always possible to translate from one language into another.
- f) difficulty in time - management

It is not surprising that the association with the grammar-translation method did not contribute to the popularity of translation among foreign language teachers.

The most active criticism of the use of translation in the context of teaching foreign languages is observed by adherents of the communicative approach, which puts the student in the spotlight, involves learning the language in the context of real life situations and focuses on the active use of the studied language material in the process of speaking, and also assigns an important role listening.

These stages are natural and necessary in the transition to non-translational understanding. Some linguists liken translation to a crutch, since it should be used when necessary and removed when it can be dispensed with. The importance of translation in the process of teaching a foreign language is obvious.

DISCUSSIONS

G. Cook (2010) argues that over the past century, translation has been a pariah in the teaching of foreign languages, was ostracized and vilified in every possible way by theorists and practitioners in this field. As a result, it acquired the

status of a “forbidden friend” of a teacher, but at the same time it continues to be actively used, although it exists, as it were, “in the shadows”.

Today, methodologists, including Ter-Minasova S.G. (2012), declare that translation is the strongest link between languages and cultures. “Since the time of the Tower of Babel, which divided people, mankind has been looking for ways to communicate between nations ... Among these methods, the main, most common and most effective is interlingual and intralingual translation. Learning a foreign language is an effective way to ensure mutual understanding between people belonging to different cultures” (Ter-Minasova, 2012, p.9)

Translation can be a good assistant in teaching a foreign language. No foreign language course can be started without the help of an interpreter. Having received a complex text for “understanding”, the undergraduate seeks, first of all, to translate this text into his native language, since he does not think in a foreign language. Therefore, at the first stage of learning, there is always an explicit or implicit translation into the native language. To instill the same skills and abilities that contribute to the realization of this goal is the task of the teacher. Translation is seen by many authorities as an important and necessary form of learning. It underlies a consciously comparative approach to teaching foreign vocabulary and grammar and justifies the dosed use of the native language when learning a foreign language. In the process of teaching translation and its use as a means of teaching a foreign language, there is a systematic accumulation of quantitative factors (knowledge, skills), which will gradually lead to a qualitative leap - the simultaneous perception of the content of the text with visual perception. The automation of positive transfer leads to a gradual curtailment of internal translation, its transformation from an intra-speech process into a purely mental process, and, ultimately, to its gradual complete elimination from the speech of mental activity in the target language, i.e. to achieve fluency in this language.

Educational translation can satisfy all the main goals of teaching a foreign language. The communicative goal of educational translation is determined by the fact that the task of communication using a foreign language requires the translation of speech from one language into another to meet personal, educational or service needs. From this point of view, educational translation complements monolingual practice. The general educational goal of educational translation is a practical understanding of the similarities and differences between the systems of

the native and studied languages. In this regard, educational translation plays a special role, in contrast to monolingual practice, which is mainly aimed at mastering the system of one studied language. The educational goal of educational translation is to understand that a thought can be expressed in the target language no less effectively than in the native language. The feeling of redundancy / insufficiency of the studied language and the language barrier disappear.

Survey among two universities on the role of the grammar-translation method

In the 2021-2022 academic year, we conducted a survey among two universities in different areas. (The survey was conducted through social network “Telegram”)

1. Tashkent State Transport University with a technical bias
2. Uzbek State University of World Languages with a degree in Philology and Linguistics.

All survey participants voluntarily took part in the survey and agreed to have their responses used in the statistics.

Since the number of teachers in both universities exceeds 50 people, only 40 teachers from both universities participated. Thus, the results of one of our studies “Technical universities against philological universities in the use of translation exercises” among teachers of foreign languages showed that 78.7% of teachers of technical universities were in favor of using translation exercises, and 90.4% of teachers of a philological university were against.

Opponents of using translation in foreign language classes argue that translation:

- 1) is a boring, authoritarian, monotonous type of activity that demotivates students and is carried out in solitude (a lonely activity);
- 2) is not related to the real context of the use of the language, as it is a "meaningless task that has no use in real life", which does not meet the real needs of students and is too academic. It is noted that translation is not a communicative task, it is artificial, and its inclusion in the educational process occurs at the expense of oral communication and the development of fluency;
- 3) negatively affects the process of mastering a foreign language, as it causes interference, dependence of a foreign language on the native one,

suppresses thinking and expression of thoughts in the target language (Druce, 2012) focuses on the linguistic form, rather than the use and functioning of the language in speech. All this makes translation a counterproductive activity in the context of learning a foreign language;

4) is not related to the skills of speaking, writing, reading and listening and is considered as a "fifth" skill, significantly different from them. For this reason, it should not be used to develop any of these four skills (Zojer, 2009);

5) forms an incorrect attitude towards linguistic means, as it leads to "obsession with the individual word" (Druce, 2009), involves the perception of a foreign language through the prism of the native one, forms a false idea of the complete interchangeability of correspondences in two languages and the possibility of their use in any context [7];

6) reduces the effectiveness of the educational process, since it takes time that could be used to develop speech skills in a foreign language.

In turn, supporters of the use of translation argue their position by the fact that translation:

1) is developing and communicative in nature, because:

a) contributes to the development of analytical, creative and problem-solving abilities [8], develops the flexibility of thinking, activates various cognitive processes [9];

b) develops personal qualities, such as discipline, interest in new information, scrupulousness, interpersonal interaction skills;

c) increases the motivation to learn a foreign language, as it makes the learning process more meaningful;

d) develops the activity and independence of students, since it makes the student an active participant in the learning process, promotes "learning by doing", develops independent work skills

e) creates conditions for the interaction of students with each other and the teacher during the process of searching, discussing, comparing and analyzing different translation options;

2) is closely related to the real context of language use, since it is a common bilingual practice, it always pursues the achievement of a purely communicative goal. In addition, translation into the native language is a natural strategy that is used by all students, regardless of the will of the teacher;

3) has a positive impact on the learning of a foreign language due to the fact that it contributes to a better understanding and memorization of foreign language phenomena, provides better and more meaningful language skills and, according to many, creates a kind of “immunity and resistance to interference”, helps to control it and creates preconditions for positive transfer;

4) contributes to the improvement of basic speech skills, in particular, contributes to a deeper analysis of the text in the process of reading and listening, the development of speaking and writing skills in a foreign language in the process of creating a translated text, which must be designed in accordance with the norm and usage of this language;

5) contribute to the formation of a more meaningful attitude towards languages in terms of knowledge of the form of language means and their meanings, develops interlingual and intercultural awareness, since the interaction of two languages inevitably “highlights” the similarities and differences of two cultures, as well as the specifics of their reflection in the languages serving them;

6) enriches the learning process, creates a stimulating constructive environment in the classroom (powerful learning environment).

A small study of the data from the survey results

Based on the results of a survey, 5 teachers of the Tashkent State Transport University decided to continue research within the framework of the university and conduct lessons in two categories: with and without the use of translation exercises and kept statistics on student performance.

The research study was attended by English teachers Rakhmonova Yulduz, Shadieva Shakhnoza Suleymanovna, Mamajanova Guncha Khamraevna, Shakirova Saida, Abdurakhmanova Zebo Yuldashevna. Raxmanova Yulduz and Mamadjanova Guncha conducted the lessons without the use of translation exercises, while the other three teachers used translation. We decided to use the same topic and the same level of students from the same faculty during the experiment, the following topics were used (according to the curriculum): (2 special topics and one general)

1. Types of bridges
2. High-speed railways
3. Environmental pollution

(But in this article, the results of only one topic were given)

The study involved second-year students of the Faculty of Civil Engineering.

Match the translation, translate the sentences into your native language and vice versa, translate active vocabulary-one word in a given text exercises were used by first group of teachers while match the definition, choose an appropriate word, match the synonyms exercises were used by the second group of teachers.

After the lessons on the given topics, a control work was carried out. In the control work there were exercises for translation, for matching the definitions, for synonym match, questions for oral answer, as well as an exercise for placing words in order.

The table 1. shows the results of students with translation exercises, and the table 2. shows the results of students without translation exercises. To calculate the percentage of completion of each task we used “Arithmetic mean formula” = $\{\text{Sum of Observation}\} \div \{\text{Total numbers of Observations}\}$.

Arithmetic mean formula = $X = \frac{\sum X_i}{n}$, where i varies from 1 to n .

The total score of each task were summed up and divided to the number of students. For example: the number of students is 48, and each assignment is estimated within 5 points and total score of 1 task is summed up and divided to 48. Thus, we determined the arithmetic mean in points, and to determine the percentage, we used the proportion where the maximum score is $48 * 5 = 240$ and this is equal to 100% and the resulting score is equal to the unknown $X\%$.

Results of the study of statistical data

Table 1. Achievements of students of the group where translation exercises were used

Number overall students-48; Overall maximum score for each task – 5

Topic: Types of bridges

The arithmetic mean of the first Table2. is 53 %.

Table 2. Achievements of students of the group where translation exercises were not used

Number of students-36; The total maximum score for each task is – 5

Topic: Types of bridges

The arithmetic mean of the Table2. is 61.6 %.

Findings

Our study showed that the percentage of students SLA achievement was higher in the second group, based on this result we CAN conclude that the absence of a grammar translation method gives better results than its use, BUT if we go deeper, we can see a significant percentage difference for every task completion. Students who used the translation method in the lesson were weaker in oral speech, in tasks for comparing synonyms and definitions, although they speak less, their speech was accurate, students of the second group were weak in translation tasks, put words in the correct order task, though their speech was better, but inaccurate, grammatically incorrect.

The study found that despite a favorable language learning context, different learners are unable to communicate fluently in English for various reasons such as limited learner English proficiency, lack of confidence and motivation. According to the results of the study, I found that the rejection of grammar translation is welcomed in SLA when teaching students abroad, and not in their hometown, only in this case they can correct their mistakes in speech, in writing in all aspects of the language. Otherwise, learners must use both modern methods and the grammar translation method to master the language.

Similar conclusions are drawn by Liao (2006), who initially studied translation strategies for learning. Shinta Sari (2021) also explored some of the negative aspects associated with student writing. It is emphasized that many meanings of this term position translation as an erroneous strategy that negatively affects their language learning. Saeed, M. A., Ghazali, K., Suffian Sahuri, S., & Abdulrab, M (2018) in a study of language learners in Sudan showed that learners perceive translation as an effective strategy to advance their language learning efforts. In this regard, Karimian and Talebinejad (2013) investigated the use of the translation strategy among Iranian English learners. Using a qualitative study design, the study found that translation as a learning strategy is used for English memorization and retrieval, language comprehension, self-assessment, as well as a communicative strategy for interacting with others in English.

Accordingly, the use of a translation strategy is also seen as a tool that relieves anxiety and stress in language learners and gives them more confidence in terms of interaction (Hebbani et al., 2010). Using their mother tongue to learn

English has proven to be an effective means of helping students understand teacher instructions, allowing them to ask questions in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes and increasing their sense of security associated with terms. they don't know English.

CONCLUSION

Comparison of the arguments of opponents and supporters of the use of translation in the process of teaching a foreign language allows us to conclude that there are not significant differences in the aspects from which they build on their argumentation, which, however, receive opposite interpretations depending on the position of their authors. In our opinion, the problem lies not so much in the translation itself, but in the approach to its use, which determines the positive or negative impact of translation exercises on the process of learning a foreign language.

Fully sharing these views, we believe that bilingual sentence-level exercises can be useful for working out sentence models and their underlying syntactic constructions. We believe that the productive use of materials in the native language is possible provided that one distances himself from the actual translation and creates communicative conditions similar to working with foreign language texts. But on the other hand, when teaching foreign languages, teaching translation is not an end in itself, i.e. educational translation should act as a means for teaching all types of speech activity: speaking, reading, listening and writing. However, with all the costs and limitations of instructional translation, it gives students the opportunity to develop basic skills in translation and interpretation.

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